

Ding-dong: Meaningful Musical Interactions with Minimal Input

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ABSTRACT

Digital Musical Instruments have given us the power to create unique musical systems of performance, often for people with no musical experience. The prevalence of gestural interfaces with a high number of parameters and limitless mapping possibilities has blossomed in this context. Yet this same flexibility at times leads to creative paralysis, contrary to the presentation of these interfaces as transparent vessels for untapped musical imaginations.

This paper outlines a new work, *The Doorbell*, created to investigate how minimal input might produce meaningful musical results. Building on work around constrained interfaces and one-button controllers, the work affords a fun, performative musical experience using only the input of a single button, encouraging anyone to discover and perform a surprising depth of musical possibilities through a household object.

By stripping back input variables and taking advantage of natural musical affordances of the doorbell, *The Doorbell* questions what elements of the interface offer new areas of exploration for DMIs more generally, and how musical narrative and precomposition are contributing factors to a meaningful musical interaction.

1. BACKGROUND

1.1 From listening to playing

On a generalised level, our understanding and daily encounters with music are experienced through one dominant activity: listening. Owing to recorded music and technologies that assist the dissemination of music, we now have access to endless listening experiences through generalised software and hardware – the activity of listening to music (as opposed to playing or creating it) reaches up to 92 percent of adults in some countries [1]. At the same time, musical performance and composition remains relatively out of reach to the very same ‘listeners’, aside from a few breakthrough apps (such as Ocarina [2]) and hardware (such as Guitar Hero¹).

There is extensive literature around the benefits and purpose of music listening experiences at a generalised level, which improve our mood, bring us greater self-awareness,

¹ <https://support.activision.com/guitar-hero-live>

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and contribute to social cohesion [3]. Yet our musical experiences in the context of consumption at a population level have been constructed with music listening as the baseline – listening is where we draw the line between absorption and creation, passivity and activity.

Digital Music Instruments (DMIs) are one area challenging this dichotomy. Unlike traditional acoustic instruments, DMIs give us the ability to translate, or ‘map’, external inputs from button presses to complex bodily movements to virtually any sound using sensors and software or hardware synthesis. It is possible to both ‘play’ and ‘press play’ with a DMI – an interesting provocation for musical participation.

1.2 ‘Low entry fee’ instruments

McPherson et al. estimate attempts in the order of hundreds to create interfaces for so-called “non-musicians” [4], particularly with the aim of generalised devices that have a “low entry fee” [5]. A quick glance on many of these device’s web pages illuminates a similar theme: “These ... wristbands let you truly create, whether you’re a pro or an absolute beginner” [6].

DMIs have given us the power to create unique musical systems of performance, often for people with no musical experience. Yet the majority of DMIs remain squarely in the realm of an interface directly generating MIDI information, anchored to the idea that instruments can be transparent vessels for untapped musical imaginations.

The doorbell offers us an opportunity to interrogate the extent to which simple design elements such as precomposition of musical materials and simple randomisation might allow for a satisfying musical performance for a player. By stripping back parameters available to map sound, and introducing a large amount of precomposition that only takes a button as input, we can take the concept of constraints to the extreme, and investigate how this boundary between listening and playing could be explored further.

2. MOTIVATION

2.1 Constraining interfaces

Limits and constraints offer fertile ground for creative possibilities, and are necessary in the creation of all DMIs. In the modern DMI environment, the high availability and low cost of motion and gesture sensors means that many interfaces have an abundance of parameters to map to sound, often cited ‘mapping problem’ [7] in which audience or performers find it difficult to causally link action with sound generation.

Figure 1. The touch of a doorbell branches into many musical possibilities.

Extreme constraints are one way of bypassing this problem, distilling the many-to-many mappings to a one-to-many mapping. Notably, previous evaluation of DMIs has noted that a “high degree of constraints led to a diverse range of playing styles” [8], hinting at the diverse creative potential of a simple constrained interface.

The doorbell is an opportunity to use as little amount of input as possible – a single button – and extract the most amount of meaningful data out of it in order to create a satisfying musical experience. By placing extreme constraints on input parameters, we can interrogate whether a simple button can provide grounds for musical performance despite the limited variables available to the sound generating process, in the process questioning the boundary between listening and playing in DMIs with a low entry fee.

2.2 Affordances of the doorbell

Doorbells are an interface of interest in HCI fields. We now have doorbells with facial recognition [9], doorbells with iris and voice recognition [10], doorbells with hand sanitisation [11] and doorbells with deep learning [12].

Musically, however, less attention has been paid to this household object. Thus, it may seem counterintuitive to talk of what affordances a doorbell might provide as a musical interface, particularly considering the limited input it provides compared to other musical interfaces such as gestural DMIs. Yet the material properties of the doorbell as a sound-making device make it well-placed to explore what aspects of DMIs in isolation might still produce a satisfying musical interaction.

In some senses, the doorbell already is an instrument in the context of an everyday interaction, especially in light of Von Hornbostel’s observation that “...for the purposes of research, everything must count as a musical instrument with which sound can be produced intentionally” [13] in [14].

The doorbell is unique in the sense that it already embodies many of the materialities found in musical performance. It is so generalised that it needs no instructions, and in some senses, it loosely has musical roles embedded within its use. Coming to the door, the arivee (or perhaps ‘performer’) presses (or perhaps ‘plays’) the doorbell

in the expectation that the homeowner (or perhaps ‘audience’) will hear it and respond.

Interaction with a doorbell is not just a single ‘push’ event. When pressed, there is an inherent rhythm within the ‘on’ and ‘off’ events – we can not only infer duration (how long the doorbell was pressed), but also two discrete events (the press and release) – a rhythmic relationship.

Thus, the doorbell clearly merits further investigation in a broader musical interaction.

3. RELATED WORK

3.1 One-button controllers

One-button controllers are a simple yet effective means of sonic interaction. DMIs such as Skoog Music’s *Skwitch* [15] and Wright’s *One-button Sound Cubes* [8] are excellent examples of limited player input providing a good foundation for musical interaction.

In the case of the One-button Sound Cube, Wright notes that the limited input provides a platform for players to “appropriate and explore the instruments within a short inaugural session” [8], suggesting the interface is both controllable and approachable – two important design considerations in the creation of DMIs.

For the *Skwitch*, emphasis is also placed on approachable interaction, with the more tactile interface affording continuous control of musical variables using pressure, and discrete triggering of notes, samples and sequences.

Building on these one-button controllers, *The Doorbell* extends work in the areas of approachability and controllability.

3.2 Everyday objects

In his seminal paper on design principles for DMIs, Perry Cook suggested that “everyday objects suggest amusing controllers” [16]. It is interesting to note that there has been less attention paid to this principle in the NIME community, with more emphasis placed on concepts that involve mapping strategies and controllability [17]. As discussed in Section 2.2, the doorbell already suggests a musical activity, thus its use as an ‘everyday’ controller or instrument seems natural, particularly with the potential for amusing or unexpected musical results.

 Figure 2. Shao Yi's *Quartet*

The use of everyday objects as musical interfaces or instruments also alludes to what David Rose has called “enchanted objects” [18], everyday items that seamlessly embed technology, networks and the internet of things within them, approaching a form of ‘magical’ interface.

An excellent example of an everyday object used in an interactive musical work is Shao Yi's work *Quartet*, as seen in Figure 2. Built as a set of four light switches which turn on and off four parts of a string quartet, *Quartet* seamlessly provides the ability to compose, perform and listen at the same time. It is immediately ‘playable’, in fact, it sometimes ‘plays itself’ when a switch is left on. Everyone knows what a light switch does, and which way is off and on – there is no learning involved, just instant music, performance and composition.

Quartet is an example of an approachable, controllable musical work that encourages simple yet effective musical interaction from an audience. *The Doorbell* continues work in the field of everyday objects and one-button controllers, using the existing sound of the doorbell to compose additional musical content that takes advantages of the affordances specific to the doorbell, activated by the player.

4. THE DOORBELL

The Doorbell is a new musical work facilitating approachable musical performance and improvisation by any passerby. It is an interactive installation, created to surprise or delight audience members, herein referred to as ‘players’, through an unexpected musical intervention in an everyday object.

4.1 Technical setup

The doorbell used in the work is an off-the-shelf HPM D641/B White Doorbell from a hardware store, that acts as a simple wireless transmitter with a range of 30 metres (seen in Figure 3).

The Doorbell bypasses the product's receiver module, and the signal is instead received using an Arduino connected to a 433MHz receiver with a simple sketch that detects when the doorbell's button is in a pressed state. This state is communicated via serial protocol over USB to a laptop, where it is received by Max² for further processing. Variables are stored based on information received from the

² <https://cycling74.com/products/max>

Figure 3. The off-the-shelf doorbell used as the transmitter

Figure 4. Technical setup of the work

doorbell, which in turn triggers sounds, sent through an audio interface to a speaker near the doorbell (see Figure 4).

4.2 Musical variables

The variables that can be extracted from interaction with a doorbell are surprisingly diverse, particularly when interactions are considered not as single events, but as part of a session of play with multiple varied presses. Beyond the simple press of the button, we can extract information such as rhythm (a press length), or the time a player might have spent with the doorbell (a ‘session’), or even intensity (the number times a player has pressed the doorbell within a given period of time).

The variables extracted from the doorbell are outlined in Table 1. While there is only a single button for all musical interaction, the system is designed in such a way that the player might unlock various musical worlds or sounds de-

pending on contextual variables like *Time between presses* and *Presses in session*.

4.3 Precomposition

Owing to the limited amount of parameters that can be used for music creation and performance, the doorbell relies heavily on precomposition. That is, most of the musical material that is heard by the player has been written previously, and the player is partaking in an activity akin to ‘arranging’ or ‘conducting’ the preexisting material through interaction with the doorbell.

The doorbell does not have a large number of parameters that might traditionally map to discrete sonic variables such as pitch (that might be triggered from one of many keys on a MIDI keyboard) or continuous sonic variables such as volume (that might be controlled through a slider or sensor). Yet this does not exclude the possibility of musical control or a ‘playing’ experience. Instead, the arrangement of the precomposed materials is key to the experience, with players drawing on a finite sample bank of sound files, the selection and order of which is determined by the variables outlined in Section 4.2, triggered depending on conditional logic outlined in Section 4.4.2.

4.4 Piece operation

4.4.1 Starting a session

Any interaction with *The Doorbell* from an idle state creates a new ‘session’. A session is defined as a single period of interaction that maintains a single musical theme throughout the period of interaction, randomly chosen at the first press of the doorbell. At the start of the session, one of thirty random musical themes is chosen. These themes tell different musical stories and explore different musical genres, ranging from a free jazz improvisation to a droning sequence of distorted bells.

Themes have been specifically designed to surprise the player with a diverse range of musical styles. Every session and theme begins with the characteristic ‘ding-dong’ of the doorbell, providing a level of continuity and anchoring for the player in the doorbell’s new theme. Each theme provides the context of interaction for a player, linking actions to musical events and phrases that are specific to that musical style.

Examples of musical themes include:

- *Free jazz drumming* – a small jazz combo begins playing as the player creates jazz drumming fills
- *Church bell* – church bells ring out, with the player performing a series of cathedral organ chords
- *Dark drones* – detuned, reverberant doorbell chime sounds, as the player introduces deep, pulsing drones

Once started, a session will remain in the same sound world until ten seconds elapses with no doorbell input, at which point the doorbell will return to an idle state, ready to activate a new musical theme and session. This retention of a session while a player is continuously interacting

with the doorbell creates the feeling of discovering a sound world, but retaining the sound world for long enough that a player could choose to improvise and explore more musical ideas within the theme.

4.4.2 Developing the session

Within the confines of a session, and the input afforded by the previously discussed variables, the possibility of a musical story emerges. By using simple conditional logic, a flowchart of decision-making is created for each session based on the variables outlined in Table 1 that fosters a feeling of discovery for the player.

The player may just press the doorbell once, triggering a ‘ding dong’ and a snippet of a sound world, or may perhaps choose to continue the piece, triggering multiple samples, notes and added textures based on the sequence and types of presses. An example of this conditional logic creating musical narrative can be found in Figure 5.

Crucially, the decision flow designed for each musical theme attempts to embody interaction with the doorbell, allowing for the diverse triggering of sounds depending on the type of press from the doorbell. For instance, in the case of Figure 5 in a ‘Jazz piano’ session, a player who has triggered more than five piano chords will find the backing track adds an additional drumming texture, and a press longer than two seconds will add a trumpet line on top of that. This illustrates how the player is not just triggering a sequence of predetermined notes, but influencing the direction and texture of the piece through the style of their interaction.

This key design aspect pushes the doorbell more towards a ‘playing experience’ as opposed to one that is ‘pressing play’. The result is a satisfying musical interaction that differs each time, whether it be a single press of a doorbell, or an interaction with multiple presses of multiple lengths that lasts over five minutes.

Short video examples of *The Doorbell* in operation can be found at this link.

5. DISCUSSION

What is it that makes *The Doorbell* a meaningful musical interaction?

Most of the musical material used in the work has been precomposed, and limited input and use of gesture prevents detailed musical control as examined in Section 4.2 – two factors that would typically be seen as barriers that may prevent an extended musical experience with a high ceiling. *The Doorbell* is not an experience similar to an acoustic instrument, and does not capture the same empty canvas and high ceiling of one. And yet, interaction with *The Doorbell* can still be said to be one of performance – the player still has agency and control when it comes to the arrangement of musical ideas and the structure of every interaction.

Mekler and Hornbæk propose five components of meaning within the field of Human-Computer Interaction that extend beyond a positive experience or simple usability: connectedness, purpose, coherence, resonance and signifi-

Table 1. Variables from a doorbell

Variable	Type	Description
Press on	Event	The downwards push on the doorbell button (the ‘ding’ sound)
Press off	Event	The upwards release on the doorbell button (the ‘dong’ sound)
Press length	Time (ms)	Time for which doorbell was held down ($\text{Press off} - \text{Press on}$)
Time between presses	Time (ms)	Time gap between two presses of the doorbell ($\text{Press on}_{n+1} - \text{Press on}_n$)
Session active	Boolean	A period of continuous play that expires after 10 seconds of inactivity
Presses in session	Integer	Total Press on events while $\text{Session active} = \text{TRUE}$

cance [19]. In the case of *The Doorbell*, two of these concepts stand out as key to a player’s experience:

- *Purpose* – “a sense of core goals, aims, and directions”
- *Coherence* – “comprehensibility and making sense of one’s experiences” [19]

Despite the minimal input and limited flexibility the doorbell offers, purposeful and coherent interaction appears to be driven by two key elements in *The Doorbell*, encouraging people with no musical experience to not only ‘press play’, but ‘play’ in diverse interactions. These elements are musical narrative, and precomposition.

5.1 Musical narrative

The Doorbell is as much a piece as it is an instrument. When a player interacts with the doorbell, there are no one-to-one mappings that allow for discrete control of something like a melody.

As Magnusson points out, interfaces like *The Doorbell* are not “. . . a direct channel for our musical thoughts, seamless media that materialise our imagination. . .” but instead “. . . epistemic objects with agency. . .” [14]. With this in mind, the idea of a meaningful musical interaction in this case is less to do with high levels of flexibility or musical agency found in traditional acoustic instruments, and more to do with the power of an unexpected, changing creative system with a narrative or story.

The narrative behind the simple pressing of a button is what gives *The Doorbell* meaning, and what allows the player to understand how they might interact with it. Indeed, musical narrative is already used to great effect to enhance immersion and emotional impact in location-based soundtracks [20] and immersive environments [21]. By using evocative musical themes (discussed in Section 4.4.1) that allude to a time, place, emotion or atmosphere, the player is musically primed to explore and improvise with sound in these terms, and ready to interact with a story and context surrounding it.

Once the first ‘ding dong’ has sounded at the start of every session initiated by a player, musical narrative continues as the conditional logic determines which presses trigger which new sounds and in what order. *The Doorbell* allows for a constant cycle of immediate feedback around the theme, and the use of randomisation combined with the embodiment of a press (such as rapid consecutive presses) demonstrates to the player that they have musical control in

Figure 5. An example of a conditional flow from the ‘Jazz piano’ session

this performance, increasing feelings of agency as they discover or unlock new sounds based on the variety of presses they perform. This process of musical discovery has been noted in other interfaces, with Wright noting the effectiveness of “‘hidden’ information that could be discovered and explored” [8].

In the context of Mekler and Hornbæk’s components of meaning, the musical narrative anchored to the physical presence of the doorbell and the familiar ‘ding dong’ creates a coherent creative environment for the player to experiment in, and a sense of purpose and direction is fostered by the momentum of the narrative within each session.

As seen in Figure 1, musical possibilities branch out from the act of a simple press, taking the player down different musical paths and encouraging a satisfying and meaningful musical interaction beyond the simple press of a button.

5.2 Precomposition

As outlined in Section 4.3, precomposition is a necessity in the work, owing to the limited amount of parameters. However, this necessity facilitates controllability and approachability, and forms an essential part of the identity of the work as a whole.

As the narrative of the sound worlds guides the player, the player draws upon roles like conductor, arranger, improviser and performer as they trigger different sounds ranging from a single note to a five-second sample. The raw materials of musical content have been composed, but what the player performs has not been predetermined. Instead, precomposition provides a safe and enjoyable scaffolding for performance, creating a sandbox for the player to freely explore within, regardless of prior musical experience.

Players unlock miniature pieces or stories, where some elements have already been composed, but where the ‘piece’ itself is only realised for the first time by the player. The original ‘composer’ of the raw samples has shaped the sound world and logic behind the doorbell’s operation, and designed it in order to inspire certain kinds of musical interaction. Ultimately though, it is the player who decides and composes the final music through a seemingly simple input parameter and with no previous musical experience necessary, demonstrating the utility of precomposition in musical interfaces.

In relation to Mekler and Hornbæk’s framework of meaning, *The Doorbell* promotes feelings of purpose as the player can build on a composition or improvisation with confidence, adding new elements to the session that are driven by a consonant, conditional logic. Additionally, coherence is fostered because the player’s actions are part of a consistent sound world, triggering precomposed musical samples that match the overarching theme of the session, and contributing to the meaning experienced by the player.

6. FUTURE WORK

The Doorbell has had an initial trial in a public presentation to gauge reactions and interactions in an ecological

settings. Within this trial as part of an open house exhibition, the doorbell was pressed 409 times over two hours. The project could benefit from more rigorous collection of input data and sonic result, and analysis along the lines of other constrained interfaces, such as analysis conducted by Wright that records and categorises input parameters [8].

Additionally, the context in which the doorbell can be used and displayed will be key to the development of the work. For instance, the doorbell could be ‘exhibited’ as an installation in not only a traditional setting like a gallery, but also as an intervention in a lobby or home, strengthening the doorbell’s connection to its original context.

Finally, the conclusions acquired more generally around the concepts of musical narrative and precomposition will be applied to future DMI design and composition.

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